

Effect of Modelling Counselling Technique on Shy Behaviour Among Senior Secondary School Students in Gwale Local Government Area of Kano State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of modeling counselling technique on shy behavior among senior secondary school student in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State. Three objectives and one research question was answered and one hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design involving pre-test, post-test control group design. The population of the study comprises of all senior secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate who exhibited the symptoms of shy behaviour. A total number of one hundred and ninety two (192) students were identified with the Symptoms; a total number of forty (40) students were selected as sample size. The psychometric property was established by the research supervisor and the researcher. The reliability of the instrument was established through pilot testing using cronbach Alpha which revealed the internal consistency of 0.79. The statistical analysis used in the study were simple frequency and percentage for answering the research question and t-test for independent sample for testing hypothesis. The finding of the study revealed that the prevalence of shy behavior among senior secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate, Kano State was at 52%, the finding also revealed that there is significant effect of modeling counselling technique on shy behavior among senior secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate, Kano State., the study concluded that that modelling counseling technique is very powerful mechanism in changing shy behaviour among secondary schools students, also the study recommended among others that, school counsellors should use modeling counselling technique as their treatment package in conjunction or isolation.

Keywords: Modelling, Shy behaviour, Senior Secondary School Students

INTRODUCTION

Shy behavior has been an issue of great concern in counselling, which led so

many researchers conducting research, researchers have been contributing to the understanding of this phenomenon, simply because prevention of behavior has become

a major focus as a matter of important to all those concerned with the education of young ones (students) in Nigerian secondary schools, shyness behavior disrupts student learning and the entire academic progress, many teachers, counsellors and psychology constantly seek out evidence to reduce the menace of shyness behavior problem among students particularly at secondary level because secondary school is an area of much stress for shyness students and is also determined the success or failure of the individual in the future education.

Shy Behaviour has been conceptualized and defined in many ways, mostly being regarded as belonging to many categories. One of such category views shyness as a subjective experience which is exhibited as nervousness and apprehension in interpersonal encounters, on the other category; it has long been described as a character trait, an attitude, or state of inhibition (Miller, 2009). Miller (2009) on the other hand explained that, shyness is an interpersonal problem resulting from extreme embarrassment, low self-esteem, decreased self-concept and fear of rejection; it renders an individual ineffective in the classroom, social and work environments. Shy behaviour reduces the chances of success, it prevents individuals from establishing effective communication in social environment, and it leads to higher level of anxiety, unfriendliness, decreased levels of happiness, neurotic tendency, lower academic performance, increased fear reactions, social and emotional maladjustment, depression and loneliness. On this note, Lyness (2009) considered shyness as that condition opposite of being at ease with oneself around others. When people feel shyness, they might hesitate to say or do something because they are feeling unsure of themselves and they are not ready to be noticed. Shyness is a term used to

describe someone who has a hard time in social situations. They lack confidence, feel inadequate, lack self-confidence, and they have uneasiness about themselves. In humans, shyness (also called diffidence) is a social psychological term used to describe the feeling of apprehension, lack of comfort, or awkwardness experienced when a person is in proximity to, approaching, or being approached by other people, especially in new situations or with unfamiliar people. Shyness is not a psychological disorder, and therefore does not warrant medication, but if bashfulness prevents a person from functioning or higher level of depression or anxiety accompanies it, then medication can be helpful (Lyness 2009). In humans, shyness (also called diffidence) is a social psychological term used to describe the feeling of apprehension, lack of comfort, or awkwardness experienced when a person is in proximity to, approaching, or being approached by other people, especially in new situations or with unfamiliar people. Shyness is not a psychological disorder, and therefore does not warrant medication, but if bashfulness prevents a person from functioning or higher level of depression or anxiety accompanies it, then medication can be helpful (Lyness 2009).

Shyness is an act of feeling uncomfortable in social situations in ways that interfere with our ability to enjoy ourselves, to perform at the level we are capable of or leading us at times to avoid social situations altogether, due to the feeling of unease during such social situations and they cannot find anything to talk about with most people especially with unknown or unfamiliar faces, Lyness (2009) classified shy behaviour into three (3) categories; Mild Shyness Feeling or Limited Shyness, Medium Shyness Feeling and Intense or Extreme Shyness Feeling.

Family background is believed to play a major role in the development of shyness. If children experience high levels of family stress during a young age, they are more likely to experience shyness during the middle childhood years and beyond (Findlay & Coplan, 2009). Surprisingly, however, if family stress occurs at middle childhood, children are not any more likely to experience shy behaviors at any point of their life (Findlay & Coplan, 2009). Children living in chaotic homes are much more likely to experience internalizing withdrawal behaviors (Volbrechet 2010). Using internalizing coping skills often will lead to a cycle of shyness (Findlay & Coplan, 2009). Studies have indicated that families with lower socio-economic status are more likely to experience maternal stress reactions. If young children experience this constantly, they are far more likely to experience shyness when they become school aged. More likely to use behavioral inhibition as a maladaptive coping method, which later, can lead to shyness as well as other behavioral problems (Volbrechet & Goldsmith, 2010). Studies have shown that mothers who are shy are generally more likely to give birth to shy children. It is believed that inherited genes may lead to a capacity for arousal within the limbic sites in the brain. Low arousal thresholds are more common in shy children and adults. The anxious feelings in social situations are reinforced by negative social experiences through early childhood; usually brought upon by shy parents (Crozier & Alden, 2011).

Shy behavior requires proper intervention, it is a behavior that affects how person feels and behave around others. It means feeling uncomfortable, self-conscious, nervous, blushing, timid, or insecure. People who feel shyness sometimes notice physical sensation like blushing or feeling speechless, shaky or breathless, it is also opposite of

being at ease with oneself around others. The researcher experience have shown that Shyness students do not participate regularly in school, they functions at lower level in school particularly classroom, and classroom do not only contain large numbers of peers and adult but also there is demand for verbal participation, as a result of verbal participation in school, shyness students participate less in schools and feel anxious when they participate. When shy students participate they talk less and provide less meaningful information due to anxiety (Gilbert, P. 2010). Gender also appears to play a role in social shyness. Research has indicated that females are more likely to experience shyness, especially in adulthood, than males. Thus, it may be more socially acceptable for females than males to be shy. (Coplan 2011). Causes future social aversion (Rubin & Coplan, 2010).

Children who have been identified as being shyness have so many problems both inside and outside the classroom. This inappropriate display or manifestation of shyness behavior lead to relationship trouble for children in schools, simply because shy behavior plays a significant role in school because it is the determinant for interacting with other, some students face difficulties in socialization, they are face with behaviour problem like shyness, shy students suffers from different challenges and difficulties in school in such way that the they lack the ability to interact with others, they lack the ability to express themselves in schools, they do not concentrate in school, they always live in isolation, they are easily frustrated and they sometime tend to withdrawn from their fellow students and teachers especially at secondary level, (Gilbert, P. 2010).

Modelling counselling technique is a behavioral intervention in which an observer view a model engaged in an adaptive behavior. This technique is aim at helping

people to participate and learn the adaptive behavior and also to reproduce more frequently and appropriately. Modelling is one of such intervention which have proven to be an effective tools at reducing behavioural problem and can be used to remove unwanted shyness behavior and create a firm of only adaptive behavior, modelling is an approach that involves the counsellors arranging a model for the client to observe and imitate such ability to talk and associate with friends and other people without being shy. The model can be informed of tape recording, programmed and Instruction. The behavior must be prestigious, competent, attractive, likeable or admirable and friendly. Modelling is a form of technique designed to help people to effectively treat different number of problem behavior such as shyness. It has been used successfully in helping individuals with behavior problem; the effectiveness of modelling has been used in behavioural treatment of individual with behavior disorder that frequently lack important behavioural skills of social interaction and confidence (Gilbert, P. 2010). Artino (2007) explained that, Modelling is a term which is also called observational Learning or imitation. It is a behaviorally based procedure that involves the use of live or Symbolic models to demonstrate a particular behaviour, thought, or attitude that a client may want to acquire or change.

Bandura (1969) who believed that direct reinforcement could not account for learning. He posits that learning is a cognitive process that takes place in a social context and can occur purely through observation or direct instruction, even in the absence of motor reproduction or direct reinforcement. Hence, the theory disagrees with psychoanalytic theory, which believes that humans are innately aggressive and that frustration automatically leads to social

withdrawal or aggression. The theory is of the opinion that people can learn new information and behaviour by watching other people, which is known as an observational learning or modelling (Ormod, 1999). The theory provides a framework for understanding, predicting and changing human behaviour. Even though, so much research work has been done on shy behaviour and so much has been carried out in the area of primary schools, secondary school, and other tertiary institutions such as, Chinyere (2012) investigated the effectiveness of two psychological treatments (modelling social skill training and thought restructuring techniques) in the management of shyness among adolescents in Owerri North, Imo State. the increase in the number of students involved in shy behaviour within the educational system and the shortage of similar studies in the study area draw the attention of the researchers to explore the Effectiveness Of Modelling Counselling Technique On Shy Behaviour Among Senior Secondary School Students In Gwale Local Government Area Of Kano State, Nigeria.

Shy behavior is one the behavioural problem that need to be address by counsellors and psychologist because it became an issue in the field of research, teachers, parents, and school management has been advised with so many ways to curve and curtail shyness behavior as a result of students backwardness academically. Despite these advises by teachers, parent and school management to make students adjust in school environment and feel secure and comfortable among themselves and to prevent the behavioural problem of shyness, the problem still persist. Some of the behavioural problem usually exhibited by shy students include: low self-esteem, embracement, fear, and lack of self-confidence in social situation, inability to

express themselves, nervousness, insecurity, avoidance, constant social fear and timidity.

Shy behavior interferes with students level of development, it affect them educationally, physically, socially and emotionally, and it also affects their concentration in school particularly secondary school and majority of successful academicians and other successful government officials to become what they are, the contribution, orientation and guidance start right from secondary schools simply because secondary school determined the success or failure of individual in the future education. Therefore the researcher come to realize that shy behavior tend to be more extreme which seems hard to conquer, it prevent students from interacting with fellow students and teachers, it also prevent them to participate in class, it do not allow them to associate and expose their feeling to other. Shyness make students feel uncomfortable and it seems impossible for them to talk to their classmate or teachers because socializing with people particularly secondary school is very difficult to them and the only way to build a powerful relationship that will give chances to social interaction in school and class for successful secondary school learning is Interactions.

Objectives of the study

1. The level of shy behaviour among secondary school students in Gwale local government, Kano State, Nigeria.
2. The effect of modeling counseling technique on shy behaviour among secondary schools students in Gwale local government area of Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Question

What is the level of shy behaviour among secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

Ho₁. There is no significant effect of modeling counseling technique on shy behavior among secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The research design used for this study is quasi experimental design in form of pre-test-posttest control group design. In this design, groups are pre-tested on the dependent variable after which experimental group is exposed to the experimental treatment (X) for a period of time. Both groups are then post-tested on the dependent variable. The average difference between the pre-test and posttest is found. Average differences are compared in order to ascertain whether the experimental treatment produce greater change than the control situation (Bichi, 2004).

However, this design is chosen due to its advantage of testing results obtained from the pre-test post-test in order to analyze the effectiveness of the treatment when compared with the control group or otherwise. The population of the study was 192; the sample of the study was 40 students who exhibits the symptoms of high level of shyness behavior, purposive and proportionate sampling technique were used in the study, the instrument employed in the study was a questionnaire title shyness personality scale (SPS) by Akinade (2012).

For the reliability of the study however, the modified four (4) point likert scale item were subjected under reliability test, the researchers conducted a pilot study by administering the instrument through the Counseling Unit to 20 respondent from the department on different occasions. This enabled the researchers to determine the reliability of the study. The instrument revealed a reliability index of (0.79), based on Croncbach's Alpha internal consistency

tests, the instrument considered reliable. The research question one was answered using descriptive statistics, in form of simple frequency and percentage, while inferential statistics, t-test for independent sample was

used in testing the hypotheses. This is because t-test allowed the researcher to identify whether mean of the two groups differ (Bichi, 2014). This was presented using the SPSS package.

RESULTS

Question 1

What is the level of shy behaviour among senior secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate, Kano State Nigeria?

Table 1: Prevalence of Shy Behaviour among senior secondary school students in Gwale Zone, Kano State

Level	Frequency	Percentage
High	192	52%
Low	178	48%
Total	370	100%

Source: Field work (2021)

Above showed the descriptive statistics on the level of shy behavior among senior secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate, Kano State. Based on the instruments administered a total number of one hundred and ninety-two 192 respondents representing 52% were identified with the symptom of shy behavior

while the remaining one hundred and seventy-eight (178) respondents representing 48%, were not met the criteria for selection. Therefore, the above analysis revealed that, the prevalence of shy behaviour among senior secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate, Kano State, was high at 52%.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of modeling counselling technique on shy behavior among secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State Nigeria.

Table 5 Mean, SD, t and p Values for the effect of modeling on shy behavior among secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State

	Group	N	Mean	SD	t	P
Pretest	Treatment	20	81.25	9.77	-.745	.461
	Control	20	83.35	7.95		
Posttest	Treatment	20	45.60	10.94	-6.884	.000
	Control	20	70.45	11.87		

Sig at P 0.00 ≤ 0.05

The Table shows the results for pretest and posttest in order to determine whether there is significant effect of modeling counselling technique on shy behaviour. The finding show that pretest mean score for treatment group (M =81.25; SD = 8.211) decreased significantly at posttest (M =13.57; SD =6.80). However, t and p indicate that modeling counselling

technique is effective on shy behaviour (t = 1.795 and -6.884; p =.461 and .000). Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect of modeling counselling technique on shy behaviour among secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State Nigeria is rejected, alternative hypothesis accepted and it is concluded that

modeling counselling technique is effective on shy behaviour among secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the effect of modeling counselling technique on shy behavior among secondary school students Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State, Nigeria.

The first finding of the study revealed that the level of shy behaviour among secondary school students in Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State was high at 52%, this finding supported the study of Jonathan & Betty-Ruth Ngozi (2017) on Prevalence, Gender and Level of Schooling Differences in Secondary School Students Level of Shyness in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State, who showed that prevalence of shyness among secondary school students was 60%; 76% of the female students were found to be shy, while 44% of male students were found to be shy), 64% of SSS students were shy, while 43% of the JSS students were found to be shy.

The Second finding of this study revealed that there is significant effect of modeling counselling technique on shy behavior among secondary school students Gwale Zonal Education Directorate of Kano State Nigeria, this finding supported the study of Chinyere (2012) investigated the effectiveness of two psychological treatments (modelling social skill training and thought restructuring techniques) in the management of shyness among adolescents in Owerri North, Imo State, the findings showed that the treatment gave rise to a slight reduction of the degree of shyness at posttest but sharp reduction of the degree of shyness of the participants at one month's follow-up assessment period and the reduction were more pronounced with social skills therapy, similarly this finding supported the study of

Iyaku, (2015) examined the effect of modelling and token reinforcement techniques on shyness behaviour among secondary school students in Kano metropolis, Nigeria, who reported that modelling treatment had significant effect in reducing shyness behaviour among the respondents ($t = 2.26, P = 000$)

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, from the findings of the study, it was concluded that there is high level of shy behaviour among secondary schools students in Gwale local government area, Kano State, Nigeria. The level of shy behaviour is at fifty two percent (52%) which indicated that secondary schools students in Gwale local government area have higher symptoms of shy. The study also concluded that modelling counseling technique was very powerful mechanism in changing shy behaviour students among secondary schools students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the outcomes of the research work, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since the finding of the study reveals that modeling counselling techniques is effective in reducing shy behaviors among secondary schools students in Gwale local government area, Kano state, Nigeria, therefore standard structure modeling technique should be design and incorporated into national curriculum of secondary schools students as additional subject.
2. It is also recommended that school counsellors should be using modeling counseling technique as their treatment package in conjunction or isolation.

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